

Acquisition of Tactile Information via Piezoresistive Array for Neuromorphic Feedback in Robotic Prostheses

Stephan Costa Barros
School of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0009-2423-709X

Vinicius Teixeira da Costa
School of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-1810-5068

Alcimar Barbosa Soares
School of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0003-1100-3533

Abstract— Restoring tactile perception in upper-limb prostheses is essential for enabling natural and precise object manipulation. This work presents a bioinspired hardware interface designed to acquire and process tactile information from a piezoresistive 4×4 sensor array in real time. The sensing approach is based on the behavior of rapidly adapting mechanoreceptors (FA-I afferents), which encode transient pressure variations during contact events. Voltage samples acquired via a STM32F767ZI microcontroller using ADC channels in circular DMA mode were converted into input currents for the Izhikevich spiking neuron model, which in turn generated biologically inspired spike trains. These spikes were then modulated and outputted as digital pulses on GPIO channels, which can be easily interfaced with an electrical stimulator to provide somatosensory feedback to a prosthesis user. The system was evaluated under different pressure and texture conditions, demonstrating low-latency response and stable operation for continuous tactile acquisition. The results highlight the feasibility of integrating neuromorphic tactile encoding into prosthetic devices, paving the way for more natural and effective human-machine interaction.

Keywords — Neuroengineering, Robotics, Real-time, Embedded

I. INTRODUCTION

The skin is a fundamental sensory organ that mediates much of our interaction with the world. Among its functions, touch stands out for providing crucial information about pressure, texture, temperature, and vibration, enabling precise grasping and manipulation [1]. The loss of this ability, such as in the case of amputations, severely compromises a person's autonomy and perception of the environment. To mitigate this limitation, devices known as "electronic skin" (e-skin) are being developed, capable of partially reproducing the mechanical and functional properties of biological skin, with promising applications in robotics and prosthetics [2, 3].

Artificial tactile sensing systems have been explored with different technologies, including piezoresistive, capacitive, and piezoelectric sensors, integrated with processing algorithms capable of extracting characteristics such as object texture, stiffness, roughness, and shape [4, 5]. Despite advances, these solutions are still far from the efficiency and processing speed of the human sensory system, which is capable of interpreting complex stimuli with low energy

consumption and high temporal precision.

Inspired by the performance of the nervous system, neuromorphic engineering seeks to bring artificial sensors closer to their biological equivalents by encoding information into pulse trains (spikes) similar to the action potentials of mechanoreceptors [6]. This approach allows for event-based processing, reducing redundant data transmission and enabling faster, more efficient responses [7]. Neuromorphic tactile sensing has been investigated for several decades, but its application in prosthetic systems still faces important challenges, particularly regarding real-time encoding and integration with feedback interfaces. Tactile processing requires not only high-resolution spatial mapping but also the ability to interpret complex temporal dynamics, such as texture and slip, with low latency. This complexity makes the development of efficient hardware interfaces a critical and ongoing area of research.

In this work, we present a neuromorphic tactile sensing system implemented in hardware, aimed at applications in robotic prostheses. The platform uses a 4×4 piezoresistive array as the sensing element, where the readings of voltage samples are converted into input current for the Izhikevich spiking neuron model, which is then responsible for generating spike patterns that represent rapidly adapting tactile fibers.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. 4×4 Piezoresistive Tactile Sensor

The tactile sensing element used consists of a piezoresistive array of 4×4 rows and columns, totaling 16 sensing elements (*taxels*). The structure is composed of a piezoresistive fabric positioned between two orthogonally arranged conductive layers, so that each intersection point forms a *taxel*, an approach addressed in the work of Nakagawa et. al. [8].

The *taxel* and the pull-up resistor form a voltage divider. In the absence of pressure, the high resistance of the piezoresistive material causes most of the supply voltage to appear at the ADC input, resulting in high output values. As pressure increases, the resistance decreases, diverting current through the sensor and lowering the voltage at the ADC input, which explains the inverse relationship between applied force and measured value. With a pull-down configuration,

the behavior would be inverted, with pressure increasing the analog output instead of decreasing it

Fig. 1. Image of the multitaxel tactile sensor. The structure consists of a 4×4 array of sensing elements, or *taxels*, whose resistance varies with pressure.

B. Signal Acquisition

The array reading was performed using the Nucleo STM32F767ZI development board. For analog-to-digital (A/D) conversion, the *scan conversion* mode was configured for four simultaneous channels, corresponding to the rows of the array. The system operated in *continuous conversion mode*, with data transfer via circular DMA, ensuring continuous acquisition with minimal CPU intervention.

Fig. 2. Hardware prototype layout, showing the STM32F767ZI microcontroller and the piezoresistive sensor connected. The interface was implemented with *pull-up* resistors and cables, following the multiplexing scheme described in the methodology.

The conversion triggers were controlled by an internal

timer, configured with *prescaler* and *autoreload* values to generate *triggers* at 4kHz. Every 0.25ms, a column was activated and read in a sequential multiplexing process, resulting in a total time of 1ms for a complete scan of the array. To ensure a stable voltage reference and limit the ADC's input impedance, $1.2\text{k}\Omega$ *pull-up* resistors were used. Thus, the maximum converter value (4095 for 12-bit resolution) corresponded to the absence of pressure, decreasing as the taxel was pressed.

C. Neuromorphic Processing and Spike Generation

Neuromorphic encoding was implemented with the Izhikevich model, chosen for its balance between low computational cost and ability to reproduce different neuronal firing patterns. In real-time embedded systems, such as the STM32F767ZI, the model faithfully simulates the dynamic responses of mechanoreceptor fibers [7]. In this model, v represents the membrane potential, u is the membrane recovery variable, and I is the input current. The parameters a, b, c, d define the neuron's firing dynamics, while G acts as a gain factor for the input current, and u_0 is the initial value for the recovery variable u .

The model is defined by:

$$\frac{dv}{dt} = 0.04v^2 + 5v + 140 - u + I \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{du}{dt} = a(bv - u) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{if } v \geq v_{th} \text{ then } \begin{cases} v \leftarrow c \\ u \leftarrow u + d \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where v represents the membrane potential, u is the recovery term, I is the input current (derived from sensor readings), and a, b, c, d are parameters that control the firing regime.

Two parameter configurations were implemented:

- **Rapidly Spikes** — $G = 1000, u_0 = 1500$ — simulate rapidly adapting fibers, such as FA-I (Meissner endings) and FA-II (Pacini endings), responsible for encoding vibrations and rapid changes in pressure [6]. Since the derivative signal used for rapidly adapting fibers has lower amplitude, a higher gain value was applied to compensate for the reduced input magnitude. The input current I is calculated by:

$$I = \frac{G \cdot |V_n - V_{n-1}|}{\Delta t} \quad (4)$$

- **Regular Spikes** — $G = 200, u_0 = 1000$ — simulate slowly adapting fibers, such as SA-I (Merkel endings) and SA-II (Ruffini endings), which are sensitive to sustained skin deformation [6]. The input is calculated by normalizing the reading and multiplying by the gain:

$$V_n^{\text{norm}} = \frac{V - V_{\text{max}}}{V_{\text{max}} - V_{\text{min}}}$$

$$I = G \cdot V_n^{\text{norm}}$$

Since operations with rational numbers within interrupt routines can be costly on ARM microcontrollers, a scaling constant was applied to convert the calculations to integers during processing, reverting the value to its rational form at the end.

The firing of a *spike* is represented by a short-duration digital pulse on the respective GPIO channel associated with the taxel. This event is recorded in a circular *buffer* along with the *timestamp*, enabling temporal analysis and reconstruction of the simulated neuronal activity.

This approach allows for a direct comparison between firing patterns of different types of mechanoreceptor fibers and the behavior predicted by the model under controlled conditions, providing a basis for parameter adjustments according to the application (*robotics*, *prosthetics*, or *teleoperation*).

D. Experimental Evaluation with Robotic Manipulation

For the functional evaluation of the system, a **WidowX** robotic manipulator (Robotis) was used, programmed to hold an initially empty plastic bottle. Water was gradually added to the container, simulating a progressive increase in load and generating “slippage” stimuli on the tactile sensor. The robot dynamically adjusted the gripping force based on the detected spikes, allowing for the prevention of object loss, a technique explored by various studies [3, 8–10]. Figure 3 illustrate the robotic manipulator and its interaction with the sensor.

Fig. 3. WidowX robotic manipulator in action, holding the bottle during the slippage test. The prosthesis uses spikes from the sensor to adjust the gripping force and keep the object secure.

III. RESULTS

The Results section presents evidence of the functionality and performance of the tactile sensing system, from hardware assembly to validation in a robotic manipulation scenario.

The qualitative and observational results demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of the neuromorphic feedback approach in real time.

A. Hardware Assembly and Configuration

The prototype of the data acquisition system, assembled according to the described methodology, is presented in Figure 2. The hardware interface, implemented on a breadboard, connects the Nucleo STM32F767ZI microcontroller to the 4x4 piezoresistive sensor array. Figure 2 illustrates the connection configuration, including the pull-up resistors on the ADC channels, which were essential for the reading scheme. The physical integration of all components confirms the embedded system’s design.

B. Real-Time Processing Validation

The real-time functionality of the system was verified through direct observation of the behavior of the GPIO pins associated with each taxel of the array. The system demonstrated an immediate response to pressure stimulation, generating a short-duration pulse (*spike*) on the corresponding GPIO pin, as predicted by the Izhikevich model. This behavior was consistent and repeatable for different pressure points on the sensor, proving the low latency and the system’s ability to efficiently encode tactile events. Figure 4 illustrates the system’s response with the pulse trains observed on an oscilloscope.

Fig. 4. Oscilloscope image showing the generation of spikes in response to a pressure stimulus on the sensor. The pulses represent the neuromorphic encoding of the tactile stimulus.

C. Experimental Evaluation with Robotic Manipulator

To evaluate the neuromorphic interface in a realistic scenario, the tactile sensor was mounted on a WidowX robotic manipulator. The robot applied controlled variations of grip force on a plastic bottle, producing discrete pressure changes on the piezoresistive array. These variations were acquired by the STM32F767ZI microcontroller and processed in real time by the Izhikevich model, with the resulting spikes modulated as digital pulses on the GPIO pins. Figure 5 illustrates the system response under stepwise pressure variation: each discrete drop in sensor voltage generated a burst of spikes,

with firing activity concentrated at the onset of the pressure transition.

Fig. 5. The robotic manipulator modulating the pressure, generating spike patterns for each edges of the signal.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results demonstrate that the proposed hardware platform can generate biologically inspired spike trains from a 4×4 piezoresistive sensor array in real time. The low-latency response observed on the oscilloscope confirms that the Izhikevich model can be efficiently implemented on embedded systems using circular DMA. The experimental evaluation with the WidowX manipulator illustrates the potential application of neuromorphic tactile feedback for grip control. Although these tests were primarily qualitative, the generated spike patterns correspond well with the expected behavior of rapidly and slowly adapting mechanoreceptors, consistent with previous reports [6, 8].

Our event detection approach, inspired by the behavior of rapidly adapting tactile afferents (FA-I), aligns with analogous studies in the field. For instance, works by Baronig et al. [11] demonstrate the use of spatiotemporal processing to decode edge information from spikes, while Romano A. et al. [3] utilize a bio-inspired approach for slip detection and suppression. Our specific focus on FA-I afferents was intentional, as these receptors are particularly effective at detecting transients and motion—an ideal characteristic for slip detection. Unlike the approach by Romano A. et al., which rejects SA-I afferents because they generate spikes even without motion, our system allows for the selection of different neuronal responses. This provides flexibility for various tasks and is crucial for future applications where a combination of SA-I and FA-I afferents could offer more complete feedback on both static pressure and movement.

The main limitations of this work include the need for manual parameter tuning, which reflects the variability of the piezoresistive material, and the qualitative nature of the current validation, restricted to controlled robotic experiments. Future research should therefore focus on quantitative performance assessment under dynamic conditions, integration with electrical stimulators to enable somatosensory feedback in humans, and the expansion to larger and more reliable sensor arrays. Despite

these limitations, the findings confirm the feasibility of embedding neuromorphic tactile processing in prosthetic devices, providing a foundation for more natural and effective human–machine interaction.

V. CONCLUSION

This work presented the design and validation of a bioinspired hardware platform for neuromorphic tactile encoding. The main objective was to implement, in real time, the Izhikevich neuron model on an embedded system for processing signals from a 4×4 piezoresistive sensor array, converting tactile stimuli into biologically inspired spike trains.

The developed platform, based on an STM32F767ZI microcontroller, proved to be a high-performance, low-latency solution for continuous data acquisition, using circular DMA for efficient processing. The implementation of the Izhikevich model proved to be computationally lightweight and effective in converting pressure data into spikes, validating the neuromorphic engineering approach for touch. The experimental evaluation with the WidowX robotic manipulator served as a proof of concept, illustrating how the encoded spikes can be used in a practical scenario of grip control. However, the robotic test was not the primary contribution of this work, but rather a validation case for the proposed neuromorphic interface.

Overall, the results confirm that the platform provides a viable basis for integrating neuromorphic tactile processing into prosthetic devices, paving the way for more natural and effective human–machine interaction.

VI. FUTURE WORK

As future work, we propose to advance the system by focusing on several key areas within the field of prosthetics. First, we aim to perform more rigorous validations using concrete statistical data to quantify the system’s performance. Secondly, the direct integration of the system with an electrical stimulator is planned to provide real somatosensory feedback to a patient. Furthermore, we will implement a dedicated conditioning circuit to enhance the precision and reliability of the sensor readings. Finally, future improvements to the Izhikevich model will enable the simulation of other types of tactile fibers, such as slowly adapting ones, for a more comprehensive encoding of texture and deformation information.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. E. Hall, *Guyton and Hall: Tratado de Fisiologia Médica*. Rio de Janeiro: Elsevier, 14 ed., 2021. Tradução da 14ª edição, ISBN 978-85-352-9591-6.
- [2] L. Osborn, W. W. Lee, R. Kaliki, and N. Thakor, “Tactile feedback in upper limb prosthetic devices using flexible textile force sensors,” *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 65, no. 10, pp. 2349–2357, 2018.

- [3] J. M. Romano, K. Hsiao, G. Niemeyer, S. Chitta, and K. J. Kuchenbecker, "Human-inspired robotic grasp control with tactile sensing," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 1067–1079, 2011.
- [4] W. Yuan, R. Li, M. A. Srinivasan, and E. H. Adelson, "Measurement of shear and slip with a gelsight tactile sensor," in *2015 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pp. 5550–5557, IEEE, 2015.
- [5] S. Sankar, A. Brown, D. Balamurugan, H. Nguyen, M. Iskarous, T. Simcox, D. Kumar, A. Nakagawa, and N. Thakor, "Texture discrimination using a flexible tactile sensor array on a soft biomimetic finger," in *18th IEEE Sensors, SENSORS 2019*, p. 8956704, IEEE, 2019.
- [6] K. O. Johnson, "The roles and functions of cutaneous mechanoreceptors," *Current Opinion in Neurobiology*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 455–461, 2001.
- [7] A. F. Russell, R. S. Armiger, R. J. Vogelstein, S. J. Bensmaia, and R. Etienne-Cummings, "Real-time implementation of biofidelic sal model for tactile feedback," in *2009 Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society*, pp. 185–188, IEEE, 2009.
- [8] A. Nakagawa-Silva, N. V. Thakor, J.-J. Cabibihan, and A. B. Soares, "A bio-inspired slip detection and reflex-like suppression method for robotic manipulators," in *2019 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pp. 6762–6768, IEEE, 2019.
- [9] A. Prach, J.-J. Cabibihan, N. V. Thakor, and D. S. Bernstein, "Pareto-front analysis of a monotonic pi control law for slip suppression in a robotic manipulator," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 917–930, 2018.
- [10] J. W. James, N. Pestell, and N. F. Lepora, "Slip detection with a biomimetic tactile sensor," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 3190–3197, 2018.
- [11] M. Baronig, R. Ferrand, S. Sabathiel, and R. Legenstein, "Advancing spatio-temporal processing through adaptation in spiking neural networks," *Nature Communications*, vol. 16, no. 1, p. 5776, 2025.